

1 **SOX13 is activated in response to ERBB2 growth factor inhibition and associated with resistance**
2 **to platinum chemotherapy.**

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7 We studied mechanisms underlying resistance to growth factor inhibition by measuring total transcription
8 in human cells using next generation sequencing technologies. We identified Sox13 activation as a
9 conserved transcriptional response to growth factor inhibition and to platinum chemotherapy. Sox13 might
10 function in resistance across setting or challenge which originates in some cell-type specific
11 developmental function or association of Sox13.

12 Citations

13 1. Gray, E.E., Ramírez-Valle, F., Xu, Y., Wu, S., Wu, Z., Karjalainen, K.E. and Cyster, J.G., 2013.
14 Deficiency in IL-17-committed V γ 4+ $\gamma\delta$ T cells in a spontaneous Sox13-mutant CD45. 1+ congenic mouse
15 substrain provides protection from dermatitis. Nature immunology, 14(6), pp.584-592.
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